

be represented as $[\text{CuLSO}_4 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}]$ and $[\text{CoL}(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2]$, where $\text{L} = \text{MAQ}$ or PAQ .

Cu^{II} ion having d^9 configuration can form complexes of octahedral, square-planar and tetrahedral geometries. Because of the Jahn-Teller effect the distortion occurs from the regular geometries in Cu^{II} complexes. The distortion depends on the presence of unpaired electron in different orbitals. In an elongated octahedron the unpaired electron lies in $d_{x^2-y^2}$ orbital whereas in compressed octahedron it lies in d_{z^2} orbital. In a pseudotetrahedral Cu^{II} complexes the unpaired electron lies in d_{xy} orbital. On the basis of g tensor values, Singh concluded that $g_{\parallel} > g_{\perp}$ in an elongated octahedron, whereas $g_{\parallel} < g_{\perp}$ in compressed form⁹. Sharnoff observed that $g_{\perp} < g_{\parallel}$ in pseudotetrahedral Cu^{II} complexes¹⁰.

The esr spectra of Cu^{II} complexes of MAQ and PAQ exhibit a set of four hyperfine lines, which result from the coupling of ^{63}Cu nucleus ($I = 3/2$) with the unpaired electron. Cu^{II} complexes with tetrahedral geometry, where the ground term is essentially 3T_2 , show two characteristic properties: (i) their esr signals are observed only at very low temperature and (ii) the g values are very widely different from 2.0023. This is because the three states of T_2 , close in energy, are connected by the spin orbital operator. The present Cu^{II} complexes, on the other hand, show esr signals at room temperature and also the g values are not far from 2.0023 (Table 1). This suggests that the ground term is not essentially 3T_2 and that some of its orbital degeneracy is lifted by the low symmetry component of the ligand field. This supports the observation made earlier from the electronic spectra of these complexes¹. From Table 1, it can be seen that the g_{\parallel} obtained for the complexes is less than 2.3 indicating covalent character of the metal-ligand bond². The axial symmetry parameter G , defined as $g_{\parallel} - 2.0023/g_{\perp} - 2.0023$, is found to be greater than 4, suggesting that there is no interaction between copper centres in the solid state¹¹. Further, orbital reduction parameters have been calculated¹² and the values of K_{\parallel}^2 are greater than those of K_{\perp}^2 , indicating that the complexes are of out-of-plane- π -bonded type. Spin orbit coupling constant (λ) for the complexes is less than that of the free metal ion (λ_0) suggesting mixing of ground and excited terms.

The esr study of octahedral and tetrahedral Co^{II} complexes is of large interest. The 4F state of Co^{II} in an octahedral field is split into three states with $^4T_{2g}$ state lowest in energy. Since these states are connected by the spin orbit coupling, the spin-lattice relaxation times are short, making esr measurements possible only at low temperatures. But in tetrahedral field, 4F state of the d^7 system has the orbital singlet state (4A_1), lowest in energy and with all excited states being at much higher energies. This situation gives rise to relatively large spin lattice relaxation times and gives narrow esr absorption lines even at room temperature¹². But in contrast, the resolution of esr spectra of the present Co^{II}

complexes at room temperature is poor due to which different g and A values could not be obtained. However, from the single broad band observed, g_{av} has been calculated (Table 1).

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Studies on Copper(II) Mixed β -Diketonates and Their Adducts with Nitrogen Bases

R. C. MISHRA, P. K. MISHRA, B. K. MOHAPATRA*

Department of Chemistry, B. J. B. College,
Bhubaneswar-751 014

and

D. PANDA

V. Deb College, Jeypore

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THE chemistry of metal β -diketonates has aroused much recent interest in such diverse areas¹ as spectral studies, gas chromatography, solvent extractions, column and thin layer chromatography, nmr shift reagents, laser technology and as initiators in free radical polymerisation². The quasi-aromatic character of such compounds have also received considerable attention. The formation of adducts of metal β -diketone chelates plays an important role in the synergistic enhancement of the solvent extraction of metal ions³. Several base adducts of zinc(II) and copper(II) β -diketonates were previously reported by us⁴⁻⁸. As a part of the general programme on studies on the linkage modes of β -diketonates in transition metal complexes the lability of the

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β -diketonate moiety was investigated. Lability studies on the central carbon bonded palladium(II) and platinum(II) β -diketonates have been reported earlier^{9,10}. This communication describes the reaction between $\text{Cu}(\text{acac})_2$ ($\text{acac}^- = \text{acetylacetonate}$) and other copper(II) β -diketonates to form mixed chelates, which subsequently react with quinoline to produce mono- or bis-adducts.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of reagent grade (B.D.H., E. Merck or Fluka). Copper(II) β -diketonates were prepared⁴ by reacting an aqueous solution of copper(II) acetate and an ethanolic solution of the respective β -diketones taken in 1:2 molar proportion. The solutions were stirred magnetically for 30 min over gradual addition of β -diketone solutions. The precipitated compounds were filtered under suction, washed with ethanol and ether, and dried in a vacuum desiccator.

$\text{Cu}(\text{acac})_2$ and other copper(II) β -diketonates in the molar ratio 1:1 were dissolved in 20 ml of benzene and the solution refluxed for 30 min. Volume of the resulting solutions were concentrated to 5 ml in a rotary vacuum evaporator and the concentrated solution was kept overnight in a refrigerator when crystalline compounds separated out. These mixed chelates were filtered under suction, washed with a small amount of benzene and ether, and dried in a vacuum desiccator.

The mixed chelates were dissolved in 10 ml of benzene and treated with quinoline (molar ratio 1:2) and stirred magnetically at 40° for 30 min. Solutions were concentrated to 5 ml, and kept in a refrigerator overnight. The crystalline compound obtained was filtered out, washed with ether and ultimately dried in a vacuum desiccator over liquid paraffin. Analysis and physical measurements were made as reported earlier¹¹. Relevant analytical data are presented in Table 1 and spectral data in Table 2.

Results and Discussion

The mixed chelates are blue or green in colour and have the composition $\text{Cu}(\text{acac})(\text{L})$, where L is the anion of tfac, hfac, dpm, tta or pta. The base adducts are either green or blue crystalline solids and are monoadducts having the composition $\text{Cu}(\text{acac})(\text{L})\text{Q}$ except the green compound $\text{Cu}(\text{acac})(\text{hfac})(\text{Q}_2)$ which is a bis-adduct. These are soluble in common organic solvents. They have fairly low melting points, and 0.001 M acetone solutions of the complexes have very low molar conductance values (Table 1) indicating non-electrolytic nature. Magnetic moment values indicate the presence of one unpaired electron expected for a copper(II) ion. The base adducts are fairly stable in air unlike the adducts of bis-(acetylacetonate)copper(II), as evidenced by the fact that they do not lose the base on exposure to air for several days. Important

infrared spectral bands have been assigned on the basis of earlier studies by Nakamoto¹². $\nu_{\text{C=O}}$ bands of the mixed chelates are given in Table 2.

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL DATA

Sl. no.	Compd.*	M.p. °C	$\Lambda_M \Omega^{-1}\text{cm}^2$	μ_{eff} B.M.	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.) metal N	
1.	$\text{Cu}(\text{acac})(\text{tfac})$	125	9	1.79	20.45 (20.13)	—
2.	$\text{Cu}(\text{acac})(\text{hfac})$	108	6	1.79	17.54 (17.19)	—
3.	$\text{Cu}(\text{acac})(\text{dpm})$	105	11	1.83	17.98 (18.38)	—
4.	$\text{Cu}(\text{acac})(\text{pta})$	118	7	1.82	17.46 (17.76)	—
5.	$\text{Cu}(\text{acac})(\text{tta})$	128	11	1.82	17.22 (17.00)	—
6.	$\text{Cu}(\text{acac})(\text{tfac})\text{Q}$	110	8	1.82	14.01 (14.32)	3.36 (3.15)
7.	$\text{Cu}(\text{acac})(\text{hfac})\text{Q}_2$	98	7	1.80	10.43 (10.15)	4.22 (4.47)
8.	$\text{Cu}(\text{acac})(\text{dpm})\text{Q}$	95	11	1.81	13.12 (13.41)	2.72 (2.95)
9.	$\text{Cu}(\text{acac})(\text{pta})\text{Q}$	107	10	1.81	12.85 (13.09)	2.64 (2.88)
10.	$\text{Cu}(\text{acac})(\text{tta})\text{Q}$	105	7	1.83	13.28 (12.66)	2.96 (2.79)

* Anions : acac=acetyl acetone, dpm=dipivaloyl methane, tta=thenoyltrifluoroacetone, tfac=trifluoroacetylacetone, hfac=hexafluoroacetylacetone, pta=pivaloyl trifluoroacetone.

TABLE 2—INFRARED (cm^{-1}) AND ELECTRONIC SPECTRAL DATA

Sl. no.	$\nu_{\text{C=O}} + \nu_{\text{C=C}}$	$\nu_{\text{M-O}}$	$\nu_{\text{M-N}}$	ν_{max} in $\text{kk}(\epsilon)$
1.	1610, 1600, 1580, 1560	450, 400	—	580 (30), 680 (35)
2.	1645, 1615, 1600, 1560	450, 420	—	650 (25)
3.	1590, 1560, 1580, 1475	460	—	580 (30), 650 (35)
4.	1600, 1560, 1580	450, 410	—	580 (25), 675 (35)
5.	1605, 1600, 1580, 1560	400, 420	—	560 (25), 680 (30)
6.	1625, 1610, 1580	430	300	700 (70)
7.	1615, 1610, 1560	435	305	690 (68)
8.	1600, 1570, 1550	450	310	680 (65)
9.	1615, 1610, 1580	430	300	690 (60)
10.	1620, 1605, 1590	435	295	700 (65)

In the mixed chelates there are two distinct set of $\nu_{\text{C=O}}$ bands assignable to the two different β -diketonate moieties. In the cases of base adducts it is observed that the $\nu_{\text{C=O}}$ bands have shifted to a higher frequency region while the $\nu_{\text{M-O}}$ bands to a lower frequency region on coordination with the nitrogen bases. Further, most of the absorption bands due to free nitrogen ligands are shifted in the base adducts. Bonding of the nitrogen ligands has been substantiated by the observation¹³ of $\nu_{\text{C-N}}$ bands at $\sim 290\text{-}310 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ region in the far-infrared spectra.

Visible electronic spectra of the mixed chelates and their base adducts in chloroform and chloroform-base solutions have been studied and the absorptions bands are recorded in Table 2. The mixed chelates usually give rise to two absorption